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Literature Review on Digital Twin-Based Container Stowage Optimization for Quay Crane Micro-Movements

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ABSTRACT

The efficiency of vessel loading and unloading operations at container terminals is largely dependent on the performance of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs). While existing container stacking or placement plans typically prioritize factors such as vessel stability or overall terminal efficiency, they often fall short in directly optimizing the operational movements of MHCs—particularly their horizontal motions and precise positioning during container access. This inadequacy results in unnecessary crane movements, prolonged operational durations, and increased energy consumption.

Current studies highlight the potential of digital twin technology to enhance field operations and energy efficiency, as well as its capability to manage uncertainties in integrated multi-equipment planning. However, a digital twin-based approach that explicitly aims to minimize the specific micro-movements of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs)—particularly horizontal movements and head positioning—through optimized container placement planning has not been comprehensively examined in the existing literature.

This study reviews the literature on the application of digital twin technologies in container terminal operations, with a particular focus on the reduction of MHC micro-movements. The literature is classified based on model architectures, methodological approaches, and levels of integration within the Port 4.0 framework. Research gaps are identified, and recommendations are proposed for future studies aimed at enhancing energy efficiency and operational performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Container terminals, which constitute the backbone of global trade, are increasingly confronted with growing demands for efficiency and optimization in response to rising cargo volumes and operational complexity. Port and terminal operators must adapt to rapidly escalating demands and

evolving challenges [1]. Consequently, the modernization and digital transformation of the entire port ecosystem—from seaports to inland intermodal terminals—has become inevitable.

The concept of "Port 4.0" or smart ports—aligned with the principles of Industry 4.0—aims to digitally transform core operational processes through advanced technologies, while simultaneously enhancing safety, operational efficiency, and port sustainability [1],[2]. Within this transformation, digital twin simulation plays a critical role by significantly improving transparency, control, and data-driven decision-making processes [2].

One of the most critical and time-intensive stages in container terminal operations is the loading and unloading process between the vessel and the quay. At the core of these operations are quay cranes (QCs), which are responsible for transferring containers between ships and the shore [3]. The performance of QCs directly affects vessel turnaround times, overall terminal efficiency, and energy consumption [4]. Given their central role in terminal productivity, the optimization of QC operations is essential for energy savings and operational sustainability.

In recent years, there has been a growing body of research focusing on the integrated planning of various terminal equipment, such as Quay Cranes (QCs), Intelligent Guided Vehicles (IGVs), and Yard Cranes (YCs) [5]. Most existing operational planning approaches and technological implementations aim to optimize the movements and energy consumption of either conventional Straddle Carriers (SCs) or automated Automated Stacking Crane (ASC) systems [2]. Similarly, digital twin-based frameworks have demonstrated effectiveness in optimizing energy usage in ASC operations and in reducing completion times and energy consumption in multi-equipment integrated planning scenarios involving QCs [5]. Furthermore, the digital twin concept has also been explored in the context of integrated maintenance decision-making processes for cranes [2].

However, the existing literature lacks a detailed examination of digital twin applications that directly target the micro-level operational efficiency of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs)—particularly those aiming to optimize container placement plans to reduce horizontal travel distances and head positioning movements during container access. Such unnecessary micro-movements increase the cycle time of each container handling operation, thereby extending the overall vessel operation duration.

These additional movements also increase crane energy consumption and accelerate wear and tear on mechanical components, thereby raising maintenance requirements. The cumulative effect of these micro-level inefficiencies can significantly reduce the terminal's overall handling capacity and profitability. In line with contemporary sustainability-driven objectives, improving energy efficiency in port operations has become increasingly critical [4].

Digital twin technology enables the creation of a virtual replica of physical port operations, offering capabilities such as real-time data integration, dynamic analysis, simulation, and visualization. These features allow for the evaluation of various operational strategies and planning scenarios—such as the impact of different container placement strategies. In this context, the present study proposes an innovative digital twin-based approach that aims to optimize quay crane micro-movements through container placement planning, with the objective of enhancing operational efficiency, achieving energy savings, and supporting sustainability in container terminal operations.

This study includes a comprehensive literature review on digital twin applications aimed at optimizing the micro-movements of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs). The objective is to support the development of a digital twin model that enables quay cranes to access containers with minimal horizontal displacement and reduced head movement, thereby identifying optimal placement or sequencing plans.

2 A REVIEW OF OPTIMIZATION APPLICATIONS IN WHARF CONTAINER LOADING AND DISCHARGING OPERATIONS

The most recent studies on scheduling and digital twin applications in container terminals are summarized and classified in Table 1 below, along with a thematic categorization of their primary focus areas.

Scheduling Approaches: The effectiveness of container terminal operations relies heavily on the timely and efficient utilization of resources. In this context, scheduling models developed for terminal operations serve as key determinants of operational performance. Integrated scheduling models were proposed to coordinate quay cranes (QCs) and yard trucks (YTs), aiming to minimize total operation time and waiting periods [6],[7]. These models were solved using methods such as genetic algorithms and multi-objective bacterial colony optimization. The importance of ensuring non-overlapping quay crane positioning and maintaining safety distances in task assignment processes has been highlighted in recent studies [8],[9]. The task allocation of electric rubber-tired gantry (RTG) cranes was optimized by incorporating carbon emissions and delay penalties [10]. An integrated system approach was developed through the joint scheduling of quay cranes (QCs), yard cranes (YCs), and internal transport vehicles [11]. Total handling time was further optimized by integrating dual-cycle quay crane (QC) operations with container re-handling processes in the yard [12].

Reducing Operational Costs: Another critical factor directly influencing operational efficiency is the reduction of cost associated with resource utilization. Operational costs were reduced by optimizing vessel service time, crane waiting time, and vehicle utilization [7]. A linear programming approach was developed to simultaneously minimize transportation time and carbon footprint [8]. A linear programming-based optimization approach was developed to simultaneously minimize transportation time and carbon footprint [13]. (Truck waiting times were minimized to prevent emissions and energy waste resulting from engine idling [14]. A genetic programming and reinforcement learning-supported model was proposed to optimize truck scheduling in real time under uncertainty, enabling dynamic adaptation of intra-terminal operations [15].

Reducing Energy Consumption: Energy efficiency is critically important for the sustainability of terminal operations. Energy consumption was incorporated into the scheduling process by accounting for the energy used by port equipment during both transportation and idle periods [11]. Mode switching between diesel and electric operations of electric rubber-tired gantry (ERTG) cranes was optimized by considering carbon emissions [10]. A model was proposed to optimize the energy consumption of automated guided vehicles (AGVs) during loading, discharging, and idle operations [16]. Energy consumption was modeled through four distinct components, achieving maximum efficiency in the coordination of automated guided vehicle (AGV) and yard crane (YC) operations [17].

Automated Stacking Systems and Crane Management: Automated stacking cranes (ASCs) and crane job assignment strategies are crucial for workload balancing and operational efficiency. Strategies were proposed to optimize delays and total processing time by comparing different job assignment policies through simulation in automated stacking crane (ASC) scheduling [18]. A digital twin and Q-learning-based approach was developed to minimize the energy consumption of automated stacking crane (ASC) operations [4]. Transportation distances and the number of re-handling operations were reduced by utilizing a digital twin-supported crane movement simulation [2].

Energy costs were reduced by optimizing the daily charge and discharge scheduling of energy storage systems using digital twin technology and machine learning [19],[20]. In these studies, models trained on historical data implicitly learned time-of-use (TOU) tariffs, capacity constraints, and load limits, thereby enabling more flexible energy management. Furthermore, deep learning was combined with digital twin technology under multiple uncertainties to optimize the day-ahead planning of integrated energy systems [20].

Table 1 Literature Summary

Author (Year)	Problem / Objective	Method / Approach
Chen et al. (2013)	Aimed to reduce truck waiting time and emissions caused by engine idling.	Multi-objective genetic algorithm (PFGA) applied for waiting time and emission optimization.
He et al. (2015)	Targeted reduction of operation time and energy consumption by integrated scheduling of Quay Crane (QC), Yard Crane (YC), and Internal Truck (IT) equipment.	Genetic algorithm combined with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO).
Fang (2019)	Intended to diagnose failures and plan scheduling in manufacturing systems using evolutionary neural networks.	LeNet-based Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and transfer learning approach.
Niu et al. (2021)	Focused on reducing operation time and costs through integrated scheduling of Quay Crane (QC) and Yard Truck (YT) equipment.	Multi-objective Bacterial Colony Optimization algorithm (MORBCO).
Guo et al. (2021)	Addressed the prevention of conflicts and safety risks in portal crane scheduling.	Logic-based Benders Decomposition (LBBD) approach.
Kim et al. (2021)	Sought to balance Automatic Stacking Crane (ASC) workloads and reduce overlapping operations.	Noisy Rolling Tide Selection (N-RTS) algorithm used for task allocation.
Karakas et al. (2021)	Focused on minimizing carbon footprint in berth allocation and container transport routing.	Linear programming combined with Monte Carlo simulation.
Chen & Zeng (2021)	Targeted carbon emission reduction and minimizing job preemption costs in Electric Rubber Tired Gantry Crane (ERTG) scheduling.	Mixed-integer programming and column generation algorithm.
Negri et al. (2021)	Aimed to ensure schedule robustness under production uncertainty.	Genetic algorithm integrated with Discrete Event Simulation (DES).
Zhao et al. (2022)	Planned multi-crane operations with a focus on energy efficiency.	Integrated digital twin-based optimization framework.
Yan et al. (2022)	Developed a digital twin-based system for preventive maintenance and flexible task scheduling.	Double-layer Q-learning algorithm.
Li et al. (2022)	Sought to solve berth and crane assignment problem through predictive maintenance.	Two-stage model integrating maintenance and operations scheduling.
You et al. (2022)	Focused on day-ahead planning of integrated energy systems under uncertainty.	Integration of digital twin with deep learning methods.
Gao et al. (2023)	Scheduled Automatic Stacking Cranes (ASC) while considering energy consumption as a priority.	Digital twin combined with Q-learning algorithm.
Zhong et al. (2023)	Aimed to synchronize Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) and Yard Crane (YC), schedules to minimize energy usage and improve efficiency.	Two-layer genetic algorithm with energy-aware coordination.
Behdani (2023)	Proposed a conceptual framework for Port 4.0 digital transformation.	Discussed IoT, Artificial Intelligence(AI), blockchain, and digital twin technologies.
Rahman et al. (2024)	Aimed to improve crane efficiency using dual cycling and reduce re-handling operations.	CCDC-DR-GA: Dual-Cycling and Dockyard Rehandling supported hybrid Genetic Algorithm.
Chen et al. (2025)	Developed a real-time truck scheduling optimization model under uncertainty using a digital twin.	Combined Genetic Programming, Reinforcement Learning (RL), and Transformer networks.
Zhao et al. (2025)	Aimed to optimize scheduling and energy consumption with adaptive vehicle assignment.	Applied Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) algorithm.
Hakimi et al. (2025)	Modelled stacking crane micro-movements in a digital twin environment to minimize unnecessary re-handling and movement distances.	Developed a digital twin-based heuristic crane simulation and movement optimization model.

2.1 Smart Port Concepts and Digital Twin Integration in Quay Logistics

Digital Twin-Based Planning and Fault Management: Digital twin technology has become a powerful tool in areas such as dynamic decision-making and predictive maintenance in manufacturing systems. Fault diagnosis models were developed using a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based approach that processes signal-derived images [21],[22]. A genetic algorithm framework based on digital twin and Monte Carlo simulation was proposed for robust scheduling that accounts for failure probabilities [23]. Maintenance activities were integrated into production planning to enable flexible scheduling [24]. Variables such as machine age and maintenance cycles were incorporated into the digital twin model to balance preventive maintenance with processing time.

The increasing scale and complexity of container transport have driven port operators toward smarter and more integrated technological infrastructures. Unlike traditional automation, Port 4.0 represents the adoption of fully connected, intelligent systems that bridge the physical and digital domains. Port 4.0 defines the digital transformation of the port sector through the principles of Industry 4.0, emphasizing the automation of business processes, data-driven decision support systems, and integrated technological infrastructures [1]. This transformation is particularly evident in quay operations, where the efficient management of micro-movements performed by equipment such as Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs) has become critical for both operational efficiency and sustainability.

Similarly, the digitalization of the port sector was addressed within a multidisciplinary framework, emphasizing the importance of restructuring port management systems in alignment with Industry 4.0 principles [25]. This conceptual transformation encompasses not only technological implementations but also areas such as governance, resource planning, and sustainability.

The Port 4.0 vision goes beyond control automation by proposing the integration of simulation-based prediction, real-time feedback, and adaptive learning mechanisms into crane operations [17],[15].

Micro-movement parameters of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs)—such as head alignment, lateral movement, and transport cycles—are critical factors that directly affect operational performance. However, the number of digital twin (DT)-supported models that explicitly optimize these parameters remains limited. Although a dual-cycling-based hybrid genetic algorithm (GA) model was developed for MHC task sequencing, the study did not provide a detailed analysis of micro-movement inefficiencies [12].

In contrast, re-handling rates during container stacking were optimized using a digital twin (DT)-based analysis that directly integrated parameters such as crane positioning, sway duration, and re-handling frequency into the model [2]. Additionally, a Python-based simulation infrastructure was employed to analyze user-driven crane behaviors.

The integration of digital twin-based micro-movement modeling into this framework may offer the following benefits:

- Reduction of unnecessary lateral movements and sway motions of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs)
- Optimization of energy consumption and cycle time
- Pre-simulation analysis of stacking plans
- Enablement of real-time decision support systems

These capabilities represent the application of successes previously demonstrated in automated guided vehicle (AGV) or truck routing systems to quay crane operations [17],[14].

Energy Efficiency and Carbon Footprint-Oriented Studies: The growing pressure for sustainability in ports has brought optimization models focused on energy consumption and carbon emissions to the forefront. Up to a 10% reduction in carbon emissions was achieved by analyzing the

energy profiles of automated guided vehicles (AGVs) based on task types using a variable neighborhood search (VNS) algorithm [16].

A graph-based model for block assignment and transport route planning was proposed with a primary focus on minimizing the carbon footprint [13]. Additionally, quay crane (QC) task assignments were analyzed using queuing theory, and CO₂ emissions were optimized based on operation duration [26].

Digital Twins in Logistics: Current Applications and Limitations: Digital twin technology offers the ability to create virtual counterparts of physical assets, enabling real-time simulation and control of operations. Today, digital twins are successfully utilized in port logistics for applications such as automated stacking systems, routing of yard vehicles, and overall terminal traffic coordination [17],[27].

However, digital twin applications specifically focusing on the micro-movement optimization of quay cranes remain limited. A hybrid algorithm was proposed to optimize crane movement cycles (dual cycling) and stacking operations; however, the model lacks a dynamic structure synchronized with sensor data [12]. Similarly, Zhong et al. focused on energy-efficient AGV scheduling, but crane movements were not considered as part of the system.

More advanced approaches—such as digital twin systems supported by artificial intelligence and reinforcement learning—enhance system adaptability to uncertainties and enable real-time optimization capabilities [15]. These studies highlight that the digital modeling of micro-level crane movements remains significantly underexplored.

The Role of Digital Twin in Loading-Unloading and Stacking Planning: Stacking planning requires the synchronization of container placement strategies with crane behaviours to optimize loading and unloading processes. A digital twin (DT) scenario integrating automated guided vehicle (AGV) routing with container placement planning was presented to minimize task completion time [27].

Integration of Artificial Intelligence and Learning Algorithms into Digital Twin Systems: Artificial intelligence (AI)-based algorithms have been effectively utilized to flexibly solve task sequencing and resource allocation problems in port environments. Task, maintenance, and energy planning were integrated into a digital twin (DT) system using a reinforcement learning (RL)-based model [15]. Similarly, maintenance and task-related decisions were dynamically managed within a digital twin (DT)-based virtual environment using Q-learning [24].

Advanced route optimization in robotic crane path planning was achieved by employing a deep Q-learning algorithm that leverages experience replay and heuristic knowledge [28].

3 FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Although significant progress has been made in the literature regarding the digital transformation of container terminal operations, several critical gaps remain in the following areas:

- Modeling and optimization of micro-level movements (e.g., horizontal displacement, head positioning) performed by Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs) using digital twin technologies,
- Development of systems that enable scenario-based evaluation of container stacking plans and crane movements simultaneously within a simulation environment,
- Integration of such models into real-time, multi-criteria decision support systems that are fully aligned with Port 4.0 strategies.

Modeling the micro-level operations of high-frequency equipment such as Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs) through digital twin-based systems remains essential for developing a holistic planning approach in container terminal operations. In this context, the simultaneous optimization of

container stacking configurations and crane movements enables the joint evaluation of multiple performance criteria—such as energy efficiency, carbon emissions, and operational duration—in real-time scenarios.

Genetic algorithms and digital twin-supported simulation infrastructures offer effective tools for solving such optimization problems, enabling the testing of proposed solutions under conditions closely resembling field reality. However, in line with prevailing trends in the literature, it is increasingly recognized that port digitalization should not be viewed solely as a technical automation process, but also as an integral component of managerial capacity, organizational transformation, and decision-making mechanisms.

Therefore, future research should prioritize not only the integration of digital twin applications with Port 4.0 strategies, but also the positioning of institutional maturity, organizational capabilities, multi-stakeholder data governance, and advanced decision support systems within the context of sustainable port management.

Figure 1: Digital Twin-Based Port Operations – Conceptual Framework

4 COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF MICRO-MOVEMENT OPTIMIZATION IN QUAY OPERATIONS UTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study constitutes the literature review and scope definition of a doctoral dissertation, within which a digital twin-supported, multi-objective optimization model has been developed to optimize the micro-level operational movements of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs) in container terminal operations—specifically horizontal displacement, slewing (head positioning), and hoisting/lowering actions. The primary objective of the study is to simultaneously minimize performance criteria such as energy consumption, operational time, crane wear-related maintenance costs, and carbon emissions, in a manner that supports both operational efficiency and sustainability in port operations.

The model is built upon a genetic algorithm-based solution framework, with each scenario tested within a digital twin simulation environment modeled using the SOLONPORT Terminal Operating System (TOS) infrastructure. In this way, the proposed optimization approach can be directly adapted to real-world operational conditions, allowing for a multidimensional evaluation of the effects of decision variables.

Although the final simulation tests and output analyses have not yet been completed, the interim scenario studies conducted thus far indicate that the model functions as expected and produces

measurable impacts on micro-movements. Relative downward trends have been observed in energy consumption, cycle time, and the number of crane direction changes.

Upon completion of the model, a data-driven, multi-objective decision support system—compatible with the Port 4.0 vision and integrable into container loading and discharging processes—will be established. This system is expected to contribute to the academic literature while also offering practical applicability in real-world port management operations.

4.1 Formalization of Simulation-Based Crane Scheduling Model

In order to ensure that container handling operations at quay areas are carried out both efficiently and sustainably, this study developed a simulation-assisted optimization model aimed at minimizing the energy-intensive micro-movements of Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHCs). The model operates within a digital twin architecture, enabling real-time representation of yard dynamics in a virtual environment and allowing operational strategies to be tested and validated. The focus has been placed particularly on optimizing crane movements such as horizontal travel, slewing, and hoisting/lowering, with their impacts on both operation time and energy consumption evaluated collectively. The digital twin model, developed using the SOLONPORT software, provides a three-dimensional and dynamic representation of the container terminal yard.

The multi-objective function developed within the scope of the model ensures a balanced optimization between key performance indicators such as energy consumption and total operation time. Thanks to the inclusion of the β coefficient within the function, the weight assigned to time performance can be adjusted on a scenario-specific basis in line with operational priorities. This flexible structure enables the model to dynamically adapt to various scenarios, including standard operation, ETD urgency (vessel departure pressure), environmentally focused planning (carbon emissions), limited operators on shift, maximum performance, time-critical priority, standard break periods, and energy coefficients. The complete mathematical formulation of the proposed optimization structure is presented below.

$$\min Z = \sum_{i,j,k} (e^{lat} d_{ij}^{lat} + e^{hoist} h_i + e^{slew} \phi_{ijk}) x_{ijk} + \beta \sum_i (c_i - s_i) \quad (1)$$

First term: Total energy consumption (in kWh), directly associated with the physical movements of the cranes.

e^{lat} : Unit energy coefficient per longitudinal movement (e.g., kWh per meter)

d_{ij}^{lat} : Horizontal distance between container i and crane j (in meters)

e^{hoist} : Unit energy coefficient per hoisting movement (e.g., kWh per meter)

h_i : Hoisting distance of container i (in meters)

e^{slew} : Unit energy coefficient per slewing (rotation) movement (e.g., kWh per degree or per radian)

ϕ_{ijk} : Slewing angle (in degrees or radians)

x_{ijk} : Assignment status of container i to crane j for task k (binary: 0 if not assigned, 1 if assigned)(0/1)

e^{lat} , e^{hoist} , e^{slew} The energy coefficient values were determined as fixed constants based on regression analysis conducted using historical operational data.

Table 2 Determination of Operational Status

Component	Coefficient (kWh / unit)	Description
e^{lat}	0.073 kWh / meter	Per horizontal (longitudinal) movement
e^{hoist}	0.254 kWh / meter	Per hoisting/lowering operation
e^{slew}	0.028 kWh / degree	Per slewing (rotation) movement

The cranes to be used in the analyses are C1–C4 type mobile harbor cranes, with a specific focus on the technical specifications of GOTTWALD brand cranes (Figure 2) and their actual field deployment (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Technical cross-section of GOTTWALD crane (excel-based schematic)

Figure 3: C2 crane – actual on-site image

Second term: Operation time (Makespan)

β : Weight coefficient assigned to time performance. It determines the relative importance of time compared to energy within the optimization framework. This coefficient ensures that the model accounts not only for energy consumption but also for task completion times. In the multi-objective optimization approach, β is used to establish a balance between energy efficiency and time performance. Its value can be scenario-specific or normalized depending on operational priorities. The model is designed to reflect not only energy usage but also factors such as service time, operational speed, and delays. Hence, achieving a balanced trade-off between time and energy is a key design requirement. The range of β coefficients and the assignment criteria according to operational conditions are presented in Table 3.

c_i : Completion time of container i

s_i : Start time of container i

$c_i - s_i$: Processing time of the container by the crane

Table 3 Assignment of β coefficients according to operational priorities

Operational Condition	Coefficient (kWh / unit)	Description
Maximum performance – time is critical	0.1-0.3	Time is the most critical factor → model seeks fast solutions, allocates multiple cranes
ETD urgency (vessel departure time-sensitive)	0.3-0.5	Time still prioritized, but resource allocation is more balanced
Standard operation	1.0	Reference scenario – time and energy are equally weighted
Limited operators on shift	1.0-1.2	Limited manpower → both time and energy are considered
Carbon emission minimization (environmental plan)	1.2-.15	Energy/carbon prioritized → time is less critical, crane count may be limited

4.2 Port Operations Planning Interface Supported by Simulation

The simulation interface shown in **Figure 4** represents an integrated decision support system that enables the digital modeling of loading and discharging operations at QTerminals Antalya Port Through this interface, it is possible to coordinate Mobile Harbor Cranes (MHC 1–4) and the Automatic Terminal Control (ATC) units, select the type of operation (discharging/loading), and define environmental and operational priorities. This structure enables the evaluation of port operations through multi-criteria analyses in terms of sustainability, energy efficiency, time optimization, and resource management.

The user can select the following operational conditions based on the scenario:

Standard Operation / Standard Breaks: Operational planning is carried out with consideration of shift planning and scheduled break times.

ETD Urgency: A time-sensitive scenario in which priority is given to the vessel's Estimated Time of Departure (ETD), emphasizing time pressure in operational planning.

Energy Coefficients: A scenario focused on minimizing energy consumption, where energy coefficients for horizontal transport, hoisting, and slewing movements are taken into account during planning.

Environmentally Focused Plan (Carbon Emissions): Operational activities are optimized considering their greenhouse gas emissions, in accordance with ISO 14064, to support environmentally sustainable decision-making.

Limited Operator on Shift: Evaluation of operational performance under constraints caused by limited workforce availability.

Maximum Performance, Time is Critical: Operations are carried out under intense time pressure, necessitating maximum utilization and efficiency of available cranes.

Within the Digital Simulation Terminal (DST) environment, various operational parameters (“Standard Operation”, “ETD Urgency”, “Energy Coefficients”, “Environmentally Focused Plan (Carbon Emissions)”, “Limited Operator on Shift”, and “Maximum Performance – Time is Critical”) were selected to generate multiple simulation scenarios, which were then systematically evaluated.

As illustrated in **Figure 4**, the parameter selections executed through the simulation interface enabled the system to dynamically optimize the performance of quay cranes and yard equipment in accordance with different operational strategies. The simulation outputs revealed that operational performance varied significantly depending on the selected parameters. Specifically, the activation of *Energy Coefficients* and *Environmentally Focused Plan* options demonstrated optimization in terms of **energy efficiency** and **carbon emission reduction**. The simultaneous activation of *ETD Urgency* and *Maximum Performance* parameters, on the other hand, highlighted the system’s strong tendency to enhance **time-oriented operational efficiency**.

In conclusion, the **scenario combinations presented in Figure 4** confirm that the digital twin-supported operational management system provides a robust framework for **data-driven decision-making, resource optimization, and environmental sustainability**.

Figure 4: Operational scenario generation and parameter-based simulation outputs within the Digital Simulation Terminal (DST) environment.

5 CONCLUSION

The simulation outputs presented in Figure 4 clearly demonstrate how different operational priorities—such as time, energy, and carbon emissions—are dynamically modeled within the digital twin environment, and how the system accordingly optimizes crane task assignments. The scenarios that balance time criticality with energy efficiency reveal that terminal operations can be effectively managed not only with a focus on speed but also in alignment with resource efficiency and sustainability performance criteria.

The scenario-based simulation results shown in Figure 4 confirm that the proposed multi-objective optimization model operates successfully within the SOLONPORT infrastructure. Operational metrics such as execution time, number of containers, TEU capacity, and task completion timestamps validate the model's consistency with the digital twin structure that accurately reflects real-world terminal conditions, while also indicating the potential for developing decision-support systems aligned with the Port 4.0 vision.

In conclusion, the digital twin-supported optimization framework proposed in this study is not merely a theoretical simulation output, but a practically applicable optimization approach for real-world port management. In future stages of the research, comparative analyses will be conducted between scenarios based on key performance indicators such as energy consumption levels, carbon footprint measurements, and resource utilization efficiency to further strengthen the model's practical relevance and contribution to sustainability.

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